

EXPLORING ENVIRONMENTAL, SOCIAL, AND GOVERNANCE (ESG) PRACTICES AND BANK CREDIT RISK IN THE GULF COOPERATION COUNCIL REGION

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Received Date: 1/6/2025

Accepted Date: 30/11/2025

Published Date: 31/12/2025

ABSTRACT

Financial institutions around the world are increasingly embracing sustainability reporting to address stakeholder demands for greater transparency on environmental, social, and governance (ESG) issues. ESG practices in banks play a significant role in shaping credit risk by influencing perceptions of financial stability and responsible management. In the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries, the adoption of ESG practices remains relatively emerging compared to other regions, despite growing global momentum. This study investigates the relationship between ESG performance and bank credit risk within the context of the six GCC countries. Data from 45 listed banks across these nations from 2008 to 2021, the research focuses on ESG scores as the primary independent variable and credit risk as the dependent variable. This study reported a negative relationship between ESG performance and credit risk, primarily driven by the social dimension of ESG. Among the three ESG dimensions, only the social score demonstrates a significant negative relationship with credit risk. Environmental and governance factors exhibit no notable impact, suggesting that heightened efforts in these areas do not necessarily mitigate credit risk for banks. These results imply that while ESG activities hold intrinsic value, they are not widely perceived as critical determinants of banks' credit risk, highlighting the potential for resources to be allocated toward other value-enhancing initiatives.

Keywords: ESG, Credit Risk, GCC countries, Banks, Sustainability Reporting

INTRODUCTION

Environmental, social, and governance (ESG) has now become a crucial consideration for investors as it affects the risk-reward profile of their investment portfolios (Viviers & Eccles, 2012). The term sustainability or the acronym ESG is frequently used when discussing socially responsible investing (SRI) and CSR (Buallay, 2019). Investors and businesses globally are increasingly focused on social and environmental responsibility as the financial benefits of such practices become more evident. In 2018, the Social Investment Forum (SIF) reports that one out of every four dollars of professionally managed assets in the United States was invested in socially responsible enterprises. This demonstrates that investors, money managers, and sovereign wealth funds are all focus on their investments in socially responsible businesses.

Banks play a vital role to the global economy's in maintaining financial stability as they strive for client trust, a good reputation, and profitability. Banks are critical for economic development and hold significant responsibility across communities (Scholtens and Klooster, 2019). Previous banking reports have highlights the need for robust corporate governance. Consequently, banks must strategically prioritize ESG principles to enhance accountability, rebuild public trust, and support sustainable financial practices (Marina et al., 2020). Financing environmental projects, for example, should be part of a bank's risk strategy. As part of CSR, executives should pay more attention to local communities, product quality, and worker development.

There is a growing in investors universals are in excessive demand for sustainable financial products. This trend towards sustainability occupies the massive potential to reform the global banking sector. It is of utmost importance to comprehend the impact of ESG activities on bank value. The 2008 Financial Crisis and the LIBOR scandal are examples of events that challenged trust in financial institutions and subjected the negligence of banks and regulators, as noted by Hurley et al. (2014) and Azmi et al. (2021). However, there is a lack of literature exploring the relationship between ESG and credit risk. Limited a handful of studies, including Menz (2010) and Stellner et al. (2015), have touched upon this subject, but their findings are not fully supported.

Financial institutions typically operate with greater capital intensity than non-financial firms, making them more likely to require government support in times of distress if not managed effectively (Wu & Shen, 2013). ESG activities can replace traditional governance frameworks by showcasing the value placed on shareholders, bondholders, depositors, and taxpayers. However, due to managerial discretion over information content and disclosure, firms' ESG performance assessments would invariably look different across countries (Abdul et al., 2020; Paltrinieri et al., 2020). According to Baldini et al. (2018), how an organization discloses its ESG information can be greatly affected by country-specific factors such as governance, and macroeconomic performance.

According to Buallay et al. (2020), certain developing countries have worsened the global sustainability crisis while others have made positive impacts on social and environmental issues. For example, the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) economies present particular ESG risks and opportunities for companies operating and investing in the region. The GCC countries, founded in 1981, comprise six Arab nations among the world's largest oil-producing countries. These countries are Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates (UAE), Qatar, Kuwait, Oman, and Bahrain, and they face unique challenges in incorporating ESG practices into their business frameworks. The GCC heavily relies on the oil and gas industry, which has been the backbone of their economies for many years. However, there is increasing pressure to diversify and incorporate sustainable practices due to the finite nature of oil reserves and the growing global concern for environmental conservation. Emerging markets typically have weaker regulations, corporate governance, and transparency (Azmi et al., 2021). The main issue has been whether ESG performance pays off or whether the costs of being a more responsible corporation are a waste of scarce resources within GCC countries.

The relationship between ESG and banking performance, an area that has not been extensively researched in comparison to other industries (Buallay et al., 2020). This study addresses the lack of attention given to banks in developing countries. Secondly, it adds to the existing knowledge about the impact of sustainability reporting on banking performance in countries that have not received much attention in the past. The focuses on banks incorporated in GCC countries, including those that have been overlooked in previous literature. The GCC countries share many similarities, including religion, culture, and political systems.

Moreover, these nations are governed by monarchs and have plentiful reserves of oil and gas, which makes them among the wealthiest countries globally. The information presented contradicts research that has proven ESG performance to be a source of improving performance and creating value. Our analysis of banks in the GCC offers valuable information on sustainability reporting pertinent to investors and policymakers in the region. This information is especially relevant to emerging economies that face similar economic challenges and aim to promote sustainable business practices.

This study is structured into several sections. In section 2, review the existing literature. Section 3 outlines the research's design, methodology, and diagnostic tests. Section 4 provides a summary of the empirical analysis results. Finally, in section 5, summarize the findings, and limitations, and provide recommendations for future research.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

This study involved analyzing data from 45 banks listed in GCC countries between 2008 and 2021, resulting in 245 observations. This study aims to investigate whether there is a significant relationship between ESG practices and credit risk in the GCC region. Previous research on the relationship between ESG practices and financial performance in the banking sector has been limited (Cornett et al., 2016), and existing empirical studies have produced inconclusive findings (A. Ferhi, 2017; Batae et al., 2021). This paper contributes to the ongoing debate about the importance of ESG practices to credit risk in the GCC countries.

LITERATURE REVIEW

BACKGROUND THEORY

The theories that discuss the relationship between ESG and corporate creditworthiness include risk mitigation and overinvestment views (Abdul Razak et al., 2020; Stellner et al., 2015). These theories have empirical support and highlight the complex association between ESG and corporate creditworthiness (Cucari et al., 2017; Yoon et al., 2018; Xie et al., 2018).

The risk mitigation proposes that organizations with strong ESG performance have a better risk profile, leading to improved creditworthiness. According to this views argues that organizations that invest in ESG factors, such as environmental sustainability and social responsibility, can enhance their customer loyalty, reputation, long-term stakeholder relationships, reducing cash flow volatility and protecting against adverse credit events (Cai et al., 2016; Eliwa et al., 2019).

In contrast, the overinvestment perspective argues that investing in ESG or CSR initiatives may misuse resources, decreasing corporate value and creditworthiness (Goss & Roberts, 2011). This viewpoint proposes that the money allocated to ESG efforts could have been used in a more efficient manner by the company. Additionally, it is possible that management may benefit personally from investing in ESG programs at the expense of shareholders, potentially resulting in reduced profitability and increased volatility.

PREVIOUS STUDY

The link between ESG performance and firm value has been conducted in developing countries on non-financial firms. Emerging market governance, transparency, and regulatory standards, on the other hand, are less stringent than those in mature markets (Azmi et al., 2021). In addition, these markets have a higher level of uncertainty (Buallay et al., 2020). In emerging markets, the financial sector's role in supporting economic growth is absolutely crucial. As Levine pointed out in 2005, it serves as a highly effective intermediary between capital suppliers and demand. Nik Abdullah and Haron (2022) found that ESG reporting practices among Islamic banks are still relatively low and vary significantly globally. Banks are under more pressure to produce social benefits than non-financial firms since they employ much more resources. Banks are more likely to get taxpayer-funded bailouts in the event of bankruptcy.

These practices are becoming increasingly important in the GCC countries due to various factors. First, there is a growing global concern for environmental conservation. With the finite nature of oil reserves, the GCC countries, which heavily rely on oil production, are under pressure to diversify their economies and adopt sustainable practices. This includes promoting renewable energy, reducing carbon emissions, and mitigating the environmental impact of their operations. ESG practices help banks in the GCC countries address these environmental concerns and align with the global sustainability agenda (Shamas et al., 2018). Second, social and governance factors are also essential aspects of ESG practices. GCC countries are increasingly focusing on social development and addressing social issues within their societies. This includes promoting financial inclusion, supporting social enterprises, and contributing to community development initiatives. ESG practices in banks involve incorporating social impact considerations into their lending and investment decisions, supporting social welfare programs, and ensuring ethical governance practices (Hadriche, 2015).

However, ESG regulation in the GCC countries is still in the early stages and remains voluntary as GCC governments and stock markets lack precise CSR regulations and policies. Nevertheless, some GCC countries have launched initiatives. Back in 2003, Oman achieved a significant milestone by becoming the GCC's first country to require companies to adhere to a corporate governance code. As a result, the Omani Capital Market Authority (CMA) urged all joint-stock firms and investment funds to partake in the Oman Social Responsibility Initiative that began in 2009 (Alazzani et al., 2021). Additionally, the Saudi Arabian General Investment Authority (SAGIA) voluntarily adopted the Responsible Competitiveness Index (SARC) in 2008. The purpose of the index was to rank firms that demonstrated more socially responsible practices. Qatar unveiled its 2030 national vision in July 2008. Human, social, economic, and environmental development are the four pillars of the 2030 vision at the heart of corporate social responsibility (Al-Hadi et al., 2016). On the other hand, Bahrain has promoted itself as an international banking hub and welcomed foreign investment to diversify its economy and decrease its dependence on oil. Many multinational organizations, particularly financial corporations such as banks and corporations, are encouraged to engage in CSR and abide by all requirements. According to the Kingdom of Bahrain, the government must control, regulate, and standardize CSR effectively; therefore, it established the Bahraini Association for Social Responsibility in 2011. Meanwhile, the UAE is at the forefront of addressing ESG issues and driving sustainability, with initiatives such as the UAE Vision 2021, the UAE Green Agenda 2015-2030, and the Dubai Declaration on Sustainable Finance (Linnenluecke, 2022).

While many studies have looked into the relationship between ESG and corporate financial performance, there has been little research into how ESG performance affects credit risk. ESG attributes could have either a negative or positive causal effect on firm risk. Numerous studies have examined the use of bond credit ratings as risk indicators. Jiraporn et al. (2014) utilized a company's three-digit zip code as a proxy for ESG/CSR scores and found that higher ESG or CSR scores correlated with higher bond ratings. Stellner et al. (2015) proposed in a paper that the impact of ESG on a company's credit rating should be assessed based on the country in which the company is headquartered and the level of awareness of ESG in that country. The author concluded that there was no statistically significant association between firms' ESG and credit rating after analyzing a sample of corporate bonds from 12 European Union countries. If a company has a higher ESG score and is located in a country with above-average ESG, it will receive better ratings. This aligns with the findings made by Oikonomou et al. (2011) that companies with strong ESG qualities have smaller spreads and better ratings, while those with weaker ESG have larger spreads and lower ratings.

Studies have shown that a company's ESG performance may not necessarily reflect a genuine concern for risk, but could be a result of overinvestment or agency issues. In a 498 European corporate bonds study, Menz (2010) discovered a weakly significant positive correlation between CSR and corporate spreads. This indicates that companies with superior CSR performance may actually experience larger corporate bond spreads. Additionally, Goss and Robert (2011) found that companies vulnerable to CSR concerns are penalized with greater spreads. Interestingly, CSR strengths are only linked with bigger spreads when a company's credit quality is low, which supports the idea that investing in CSR activities may not be the most efficient use of company resources.

A study conducted by Izzo and Magnanelli (2012) on 332 firms in France, Germany, Italy, and Japan. Their findings showed that there was no indication of a link between CSR and increased cost of debt. However, their findings did reveal a positive association between firms with higher CSR and a higher cost of debt, in line with Menz's (2010) research. It was found by Baran and Zhang (2012) that the yield spreads of newly issued bonds increased after companies were included in the KLD 400 Index, which is made up of businesses with outstanding CSR performance. This is in line with the conclusions reached by Menz (2010) and Izzo and Magnanelli (2012). The research findings on the impact of ESG or CSR on credit risk appear to be conflicting. Nonetheless, the studies all seek to measure how ESG performance affects credit risk. Therefore, this study hypothesizes that:

H1: ESG score affects a bank's credit risk in GCC countries.

H2: Environmental, social and governance practices affect a bank's credit risk in GCC countries.

METHODOLOGY

DATA

This study uses the data from Refinitiv Eikon, hosted by Thomson Reuters. This study's initial sample consists of 63 listed banks from GCC with financial and ESG data provided by Refinitiv database from 2008 to 2021. The preliminary screening reveals that some banks do not supply the data required to assess the degree of ESG performance. Following Buallay et al. (2019), for a bank to be included in the sample, it should have data for at least two years. Finally, the study obtained a sample of 45 banks for 2008 -2021, resulting in 245 bank-year observations. To reduce the impact of outliers, winsorize all variables at 1%.

VARIABLES

Three disclosure indicators (environmental, social, and governance) measure the independent variable (ESG practices). The study chose Refinitiv to collect ESG data because it is a trusted international database with one of the most extensive ESG data sets available, comprising more than 450 different ESG measures with historical data. Researchers frequently use this database (Bătae et al., 2021; Eliwa et al., 2019; Stellner et al., 2015), and it has a transparent ESG data process available on its official web pages.

The dependent variables (credit risk) have been measured using the loan loss reserve ratio to total loan (Abedifar et al., 2012; Lepetit et al., 2008a; Gonzalez, 2005). This variable considers both the expected future performance and the historical performance of the current loan portfolio. In the income statement, a loan loss provision represents its recurring adjustment. However, the credit risk indicator used in this study only reflects a part of the loan portfolio's quality, as differences in loan classification, reserve requirements, and write-off policies may exist between banks.

The variables used to explain credit risk in this study are bank size, profitability, leverage, gross domestic product (GDP) growth, country governance index (CGI) and country inflation. The definitions of the variables used in the models and the sources from which they were derived are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Definition and Source of Information

Variables	Labels	Measurements
Dependent variable (Source: Refinitiv Eikon Datastream)		
Credit Risk	DCR	The ratio of loan loss reserves to total deposit
Independent Variable (Source: Refinitiv Eikon Datastream)		
ESG Score	ESG	Represents the weighted average of the ESG scores to comprehensively evaluate the sustainability impact and corporate conduct.
Environmental Score	ENV	The environmental dimension of ESG performance.
Social Score	SOC	The social dimension of ESG performance.
Governance Score	GOV	The governance dimension of ESG performance.
Control Variable (Source: Refinitiv Eikon Datastream)		
Bank Size	SIZE	Natural logarithm of bank's market capitalization
Profitability	ROA	Pretax income/total assets
Leverage	LEV	The ratio of long-term debt over total assets
GDP growth	GDP	Percentage change in GDP
Country Governance Index	CGI	The total score of the World Governance Indicators (WGI) index includes six governance indicators: Voice and Accountability, Political Stability, Government Effectiveness, Regulatory Quality, Rule of Law, and Control of Corruption.
Inflation	INF	Inflation rate

MODEL DEVELOPMENT

To explain the relationship between bank's credit risk and ESG, this study specify the following model:

$$DCR_{i,t} = ESG_{i,t} + Control\ Variables_{i,t} + e_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

The above model represents credit risk as to the function of ESG score and the control variables. This paper introduce the ESG score in the model without an environmental score (ENV), social score (SOC), and governance score (GOV) to avoid the possibility high degree of collinearity between the ESG score and the elements constituting the ESG score. Thus, this study separate the environmental score (ENV), social score (SOC), and governance score (GOV) from the ESG score (ESG) in the constructed model; hence, two models to explain the relationship between ESG on credit risk. The elements of the ESG constitute the second model to explain the relationship of ESG with credit risk:

$$DCR_{i,t} = ENV_{i,t} + SOC_{i,t} + GOV_{i,t} + Control\ Variables_{i,t} + e_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

The second model explains credit risk as the function of the ESG's elements and the control variables. It addresses identifying the component of ESG that have a significant relationship with credit risk.

METHODOLOGY

This study started with estimating panel data regression models of bank credit risk as a function of ESG components and various control measures. This study used the Lagrange multiplier test developed by Breusch and Pagan in 1980 to determine whether pooled ordinary least squares (OLS) is a suitable model. Significant test statistics imply that pooled OLS regression with unobserved heterogeneity would provide biased estimates. In reporting the research findings of this study, the fixed effects estimator is the most suitable choice for our data. A parameter is estimated by the fixed effects model for each cross-sectional unit (i.e., each bank). To assess for serial autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity, this study conducted additional tests. First, estimated serial autocorrelation using Wooldridge's method (2010). A significant test statistic showed that our data exhibited serial correlation. Secondly, the modified Waldtest for groupwise heteroscedasticity revealed that heteroscedasticity also affected our data. Then recalculated t-values with the bank's clustered standard errors to alleviate concerns regarding cross-sectional and time-series dependence and heteroscedasticity.

RESULTS

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

This study analyzed various variables and their summary statistics as shown in Table 2. The sample banks have an average credit risk of 6. The results from our descriptive analysis revealed that the governance score has the highest means, followed by ESG and social scores. On the other hand, environmental disclosure has the lowest score. This study found that the average levels of governance disclosure are not surprising, as banks must comply with corporate governance codes' disclosure requirements. Additionally, the banking business has little impact on the environment, which explains the lack of environmental disclosure. The variations in disclosure levels indicate that some are mandatory, while others are voluntary.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
<i>Dependent variable</i>					
DCR	245	5.528	7.093	0	57.38
<i>Key variables</i>					
ESG	245	37.708	16.07	9.05	74.11
ENV	245	23.48	22.137	0	75.72
SOC	245	32.387	18.765	3.4	74.1
GOV	245	54.147	20.981	5.33	89.35
<i>Control variables</i>					
SIZE	245	2.848	.062	2.687	2.966
ROA	245	4.117	.015	4.043	4.147
LEV	245	2.578	.83	-.094	3.577
CGI	245	1.55	.461	.649	2.076
INF	245	1.76	.381	.9	2.336
GDPCh	245	2.337	.499	.135	3.388

REGRESSION RESULTS

Table 3. Regression Result

Model	(1)	(2)
ESG	-0.00477(0.0214)	
ENV		0.0157(0.0188)
SOC		-0.0465*(0.0240)
GOV		0.0345(0.0324)
SIZE	2.242(34.47)	13.29(39.92)
ROA	-23.93(45.14)	-21.89(44.61)
LEV	-0.426(0.874)	-0.511(0.943)
CGI	-4.378*** (1.519)	-3.288** (1.330)
INF	1.565(1.446)	1.489(1.568)
GDPCh	-0.744(0.728)	-0.864(0.711)
Constant	104.7(265.5)	62.86(278.1)
Observations	245	245
Number of Id	45	45

Notes: * significant at 10%, ** significant at 5%, *** significant at 1%.

This study aims to examine the relationship between ESG performance and bank credit risk in the GCC countries. To achieve the aim of the study, this study employ multivariate regression in two ways. Firstly, credit risk is regressed on the ESG score and control variables. It is addressed to examine the effect of ESG on credit risk. Secondly, credit risk is regressed on the elements that constitute the ESG: Environmental (ENV), Social (SOC), and governance (GOV) score, with additional control variables to identify which component of ESG affects the credit risk.

Table 3 presents the result of the multivariate regression over the two models in this study. The results provide insights into the relationship between ESG performance and bank credit risk in the the GCC countries. Model 1 indicates a negative but statistically insignificant relationship between the aggregate ESG score and credit risk, while Model 2 reveals that only the social component of ESG exhibits a statistically significant and negative association with credit risk. These findings suggest a differentiated impact of ESG dimensions on bank risk profiles, warranting a more focused approach when assessing ESG effectiveness.

The insignificant influence of the overall ESG score, the environmental and governance dimensions individually may reflect the emerging state of ESG integration in GCC banking practices. In many GCC countries, ESG disclosures remain largely voluntary and often lack uniformity or depth. As such, ESG performance may not yet be systematically embedded into banks' strategic risk management frameworks, potentially diluting its impact on credit risk mitigation. This result aligns with the overinvestment hypothesis, which posits that without robust ESG integration, such efforts may be perceived as inefficient, failing to deliver tangible risk-reducing benefits.

The significant negative relationship between the social score and credit risk is notable. It suggests that banks that actively engage in socially responsible activities are perceived as more stable and trustworthy institutions. These social efforts may enhance stakeholder relationships, reduce reputational risk, and improve borrower creditworthiness, ultimately contributing to lower loan loss reserves. This supports the risk mitigation theory, which emphasizes how ESG engagement can reduce exposure to non-financial risks and foster long-term sustainability.

Cultural and institutional factors may also play a critical role in explaining this outcome. In the GCC context, social responsibility is deeply embedded in Islamic and regional values, often manifesting through zakat, waqf, and other community-driven initiatives. Banks that align with

these social expectations may be rewarded with enhanced stakeholder loyalty and customer confidence, thereby reducing the likelihood of credit defaults.

The lack of significant findings for environmental and governance dimensions warrants further examination. On the environmental front, the relatively low impact may be due to the banking sector's limited direct environmental footprint. Banks, unlike industrial firms, do not emit pollution or deplete natural resources in their core operations, making environmental disclosures less salient to credit risk assessments. Moreover, many environmental initiatives result in higher production costs, potentially impacting profitability (Klassen & McLaughlin, 1996). This perception could discourage banks from investing in environmental activities, as they may require more extended payback periods, making them less attractive in the short run.

For governance, while GCC banks often operate under strict corporate governance codes, especially those aligned with Shariah compliance, the high governance scores may reflect regulatory compliance rather than proactive, value-adding governance innovation. This could explain the muted effect on credit risk. Additionally, governance structures in the region—often influenced by state ownership or royal family participation—may produce governance indicators that do not fully capture agency problems or management discipline, limiting their predictive power over risk outcomes.

CONCLUSION

This paper studies the association of ESG performance with bank credit risk, measured by the loan-loss reserve to total loan ratio, of listed banks in emerging markets, specifically in the GCC countries. Only a few research look into the ESG link against credit risk is as the dependent variable. Furthermore, as described in the preceding research section, the findings from these studies significantly differ in the relationship between the two. From the risk mitigation perspective, firms can reduce their exposure to risk by adopting ESG initiatives that foster stronger relationships with key stakeholders. On the other hand, the overinvestment view argues that ESG activities may be perceived as resource-draining activities that serve managerial interests rather than shareholder value, potentially leading to higher credit risk. Therefore, according to Stellner et al. (2015), rational investors should only consider ESG investments to be value-enhancing and risk-reducing if the marginal gains exceed the marginal expenses.

This study found a negative relationship between ESG performance and credit risk based on a sample of 45 publicly listed banks from six GCC countries between 2008 and 2021. Next, analyse the three dimensions of ESG to determine which dimension impacts bank credit risk. Only social score demonstrates a significant negative association with credit risk. The lack of association between environmental and governance activities and credit risk suggests that increased ESG activity does not reduce banks' credit risk. It indicates that banks should be mindful of the diminishing influence of ESG activity on credit risk and be more efficient in allocating resources for ESG activities.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Similar to earlier research on emerging markets, particularly in the GCC countries, the sample consists of only 45 banks, which may be considered a small sample compared to developed capital markets. Second limitation include the data collection comprises only listed banks in GCC nations with at least two years of data available in the Refinitiv database from 2008 to 2021. Although Refinitiv's data-gathering procedure is not transparent, ESG data measurements are subject to many audit assessments conducted by database managers, implying that they are more accurate than self-collected data. Despite its limitations, this study makes a significant contribution by being the first to investigate the effect of sustainability

reporting on the credit risk performance of banks listed in the GCC countries. In conclusion, our high-quality data sample gives an initial picture of the relationship between ESG performance and credit risk in the GCC banking sector.

The findings suggest that policymakers could benefit from additional research into the value of specific ESG activities to developing market banks and their communities. Once authorities have identified the activities providing banks with the most value, they can modify regulatory requirements to encourage them to participate. By highlighting the benefits of specific ESG activities which can increase ESG adoption in emerging markets and convince institutions that they would only have taken such measures if they had taken them. Future research may also investigate the impact of the Coronavirus outbreak on the financial sector and the challenges institutions face as they restructure their business strategies.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors thank Faculty of Accountancy, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Cawangan Selangor, Kampus Puncak Alam, Selangor, Malaysia, IIUM Institute of Islamic Banking and Finance, International Islamic University Malaysia, and Faculty of Business, UNITAR University College Kuala Lumpur for the support of the publication of this research.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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